

Cation Chromatography on Sn(IV)hexacyanoferrate(II) Papers in Carboxylic Acids, DMSO and HNO₃ Systems : Separation of Metal Ions

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Chromatographic studies of metal ions on Sn(IV)hexacyanoferrate(II) papers using formic, acetic, oxalic, citric and tartaric acid, DMSO and HNO₃ systems have been reported and effect of carboxylic acids used, DMSO and different concentration of HNO₃ on the movement of metal ions has been observed. Also the effect of the charge on the metal ions on their R_f values has been discussed. The utility of the paper and solvent systems have been demonstrated by achieving a large number of binary separations.

THE present work is to explore the potentiality of various acids as solvents in the chromatographic studies on papers impregnated with Sn(IV)hexacyanoferrate(II) ion exchanger¹⁻⁴.

Experimental

Paper strips of the required size were dipped in a 0.1M aqueous Sn(IV)chloride for 10 seconds. After drying they were dipped in a 0.1M K₄Fe(CN)₆ for 5 seconds and were dried again at room temperature. They were then washed with distilled water to remove excess reagent. The strips were finally dried and used as such. Some strips were also impregnated with 0.2M and 0.5M reagent solutions respectively for a comparative study. The ascending technique was used in the ordinary glass jars.

Chromatographic behaviour of various metal ions has been studied.

The solvent systems used were:—(i) Distilled water; (ii) 0.5M formic, acetic, oxalic, citric and tartaric acids; (iii) 0.5M sodium formate, sodium oxalate, sodium citrate and ammonium acetate; (iv) 0.2M ammonium oxalate; (v) (1,5,10,20,40) × 10⁻¹M HNO₃ and (vi) (DMSO : 8M HNO₃) in the volume ratios 9 : 1, 7 : 3, 5 : 5, 3 : 7, 1 : 9.

Discussion

The different acids used here were of varying pK values and also of varying basicity. The results show that the movement of the metals on plain paper is always greater than on impregnated paper.

The ion exchange behaviour of the material deposited on the paper retards the movement of the metals. The metals like Cu, Cd, Pd, Mn, Co, Ni, VO, UO₂, Au, Pt, Ti, Nb, Ga and Zr showed negligible movement on ferrocyanide papers, possibly because they form insoluble ferrocyanides. The alkali metals (K, Rb) appreciably moved on both plain and impregnated papers. Also their R_f values were similar. Since alkali ferrocyanides are soluble the movement of alkali metals on Sn(IV)ferrocyanide papers is not effected. Also due to the non-complexing nature of these metals their movement is independent of the acid used. Tl, Sb, Pb, Mo and Bi, however, show a different behaviour. Their R_f value is high in oxalic acid, decreases in tartaric acid and remains constant in citric, formic and acetic acids. A high K_a value of oxalic acid (5400 × 10⁻⁶) may be responsible for a higher movement of metal ions in this system. Fe, Cr and As show the R_f value to be lowest in oxalic acid and highest in acetic acid probably because they form insoluble oxalates.

To see the effect of the charge on the metal ion on its movement the R_f values of all the metal ions having same charge were averaged and plotted against the charge of the metal ion. These plots indicate that the monovalent metals move faster on impregnated papers. The movement decreases as the charge on metal ion increases. However, in tartaric acid medium some irregularity was observed, where the R_f value decreases from monovalent to the pentavalent metals and then sharply increases for the hexavalent ones. Almost all metal ions show a high selectivity for the exchanger in all concentrations of HNO₃; Be, Ni, Co, Ba and Nd are the exceptions to this behaviour. They move appreciably in all the HNO₃ concentrations.

In presence of DMSO also, the high selectivity of the material for the metal ions studied has been observed. Tl, Pb, Ba, Ce(III) and Th are the only few metals showing an appreciable movement in different ratios of DMSO-50% HNO₃ systems. Based on these observations some very good separations have been found possible on these different solvent systems. Table 1 summarizes the

TABLE 1(a)—BINARY SEPARATIONS ON Sn(IV)HEXACYANOFERRATE PAPERS IN DMSO : 50% HNO₃

Solvent systems	Separations
DMSO & 50% HNO ₃ (1 : 1)	Ag - Pb, Hg(I) - Pb, Hg(II) - Pb, Cu - Pb, Bi - Pb, Ag - Tl, Hg(I) - Tl, Hg(II) - Tl, Cu - Tl.
DMSO & 50% HNO ₃ (7 : 3)	Ag - Pb, Bi - Pb.
DMSO & 50% HNO ₃ (5 : 5)	Bi - Pb.
DMSO & 50% HNO ₃ (3 : 7)	Cu - Pb, Pr - Nd
DMSO & 50% HNO ₃ (1 : 9)	Cu - Pb, Ti - Th, Ti - Nd, Pr - Nd.

TABLE 1(b)—BINARY SEPARATIONS ON Sn(IV)HEXACYANOFERRATE PAPERS IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF HNO₃

Solvent systems	Separations
0.1M HNO ₃	Al - Be, Ga - Be.
0.5M HNO ₃	Al - Be, Co - Ni, Zn - Mn, Ga - Bi, Al - Be, Ga - Be, Ag - Pb, Cu - Pb, Bi - Pb, Ag - Tl, Sb - Tl, Cu - Tl.
1M HNO ₃	Zr - Pr, Zr - Ce, Au - Pt, W - Pt, Mo - Pt, Zr - Nd, Zr - La, Zr - Ir, Ga - Bi.
4M HNO ₃	Al - Be, Ga - Be, Bi - Pb, Cu - Pb, Ag - Pb, Cu - Tl, Ag - Tl.

TABLE 1(c)—BINARY SEPARATIONS ON Sn(IV)HEXACYANOFERRATE(II) PAPERS IN CARBOXYLIC ACID SOLUTIONS

Solvent systems	Separations
Oxalic acid	Cu - Zn, Ag - Tl, VO - Mo.
Tartaric acid	Zn - Mg, Cr - W, UO ₂ - Mo.
Sodium oxalate	Pb - UO ₂ , W - UO ₂ , Zr - UO ₂ , Nd - UO ₂ .
Sodium citrate	Cr - Mo, In - UO ₂ , Th - UO ₂ .
Ammonium oxalate	Hg(I) - Hg(II), Ag - Hg(II), Ag - Tl, Zn - Hg(II), Cd - Hg(II).

separations achieved in the carboxylic acid systems. The main advantage of this study, therefore, is that the important separations can be achieved in much less time than the conventional methods using very common and easily available chemicals such as HNO₃ and carboxylic acids. Another advantage of this study is that the separations required less time than many other methods of separations.

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